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Case Report

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Aortic Dissection With Isolated Bradycardia and Epigastric Pain: a Case Report

ABSTRACT

Aortic dissection is typically an emergency condition characterised by sudden onset of back pain, tearing-like chest pain, dizziness, vomiting, and sweating. In this case, we aimed to present a case of silent aortic dissection accompanied by isolated bradycardia and epigastric pain. A 74-year-old male patient with known diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary artery disease, cholesterol and arrhythmia presented to the district state hospital with sudden onset epigastric pain at home. The patient's tests in the district were normal, but he was referred to our hospital due to his newly developed bradycardia and persistent epigastric pain. The patient, who did not present with a severe clinical picture and was found to have a Stanford Type A dissection on computed tomography angiography, underwent emergency surgery by the Department of Cardiovascular Surgery.

Keywords: Bradycardia, Epigastric Pain, Aortic Dissection, Emergency Department

Introduction

Aortic dissection is typically an acute surgical emergency characterised by sudden onset of back pain, tearing chest pain, dizziness, vomiting, and sweating, which can progress to a fatal course within

minutes to hours. It has a mortality rate of 33%, 50%, and 75% at 24 hours, 48 hours, and 2 weeks, respectively (1-2). We present a case of silent aortic dissection accompanied by isolated bradycardia and epigastric pain.

Aortic dissection involves various risk factors, with hypertension and known connective tissue diseases being the most common. Patients most frequently present with sudden-onset severe chest or back pain not accompanied by myocardial ischaemia. Increased severe chest or back pain after strenuous exercise or drug use strongly suggests acute aortic dissection. Patients typically describe sudden onset of the worst pain they have ever experienced, radiating from the chest to the lower back. Neurological symptoms, including central nervous system symptoms such as syncope, and various spinal symptoms such as paraparesis or paraplegia, may also be the first symptoms, albeit rarely (1).

Case Report

A 74-year-old male patient with known diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary artery disease, high cholesterol and arrhythmia presented to the district state hospital complaining of sudden onset epigastric pain and fainting at home. Following normal findings on examination at the district state hospital, the patient was

transferred to our hospital with a provisional diagnosis of acute coronary syndrome, having been administered 300 mg of aspirin, due to the presence of newly developed bradycardia and persistent epigastric pain, with troponin testing and cardiology consultation requested.

The patient brought in by 112 was in good general condition, not sweating, with a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15. Breathing sounds were normal on auscultation, there was no neurological deficit, blood pressure was 120/72 mmHg, and pulses were present in all four extremities. The patient reported isolated epigastric pain, and the ECG showed sinus bradycardia with a rate of 48/min (Figure 1). Laboratory parameters were as follows: haemoglobin 13.2 g/dl, WBC 9860 μ , platelets 180,000 μ L, creatinine 1.13 mg/dl, total bilirubin 0.8 mg/dl, CRP 0.1 mg/L, INR 1.1, troponin 0.006 ng/ml, blood gas was normal.

As the patient's epigastric pain did not subside and the patient described presyncope, a control troponin test was taken and computed tomography angiography was performed on the upper and lower abdomen and in the dissection phase.

The patient was referred to cardiology due to bradycardia and epigastric pain. Given the bradycardia responding to atropine and the

epigastric pain, a follow-up consultation was recommended with a control troponin result.

The patient, who was observed to have a Stanford-A aortic dissection on computed tomography angiography, was referred to cardiac and vascular surgery. The echocardiogram performed by cardiology showed an ejection fraction of 60%, mild aortic insufficiency, and a dissection flap in the ascending aorta (Figure 2). The computed tomography angiography report stated, 'The ascending aorta diameter was measured at approximately 47 mm and was dilated. an intimal flap consistent with a DeBakey I-Stanford type A dissection extending from the level of the ascending aorta to the aortic arch, descending aorta, abdominal aorta, and both common iliac arteries and the right external iliac artery' (Figures 3-4-5-6).

Our patient was taken into emergency surgery by the Cardiovascular Surgery Department and passed away at the end of the 7-hour operation.

Discussions

An analysis conducted in the International Acute Aortic Dissection Registry reported that the average age of aortic dissection was 63, it was more common in men (65%), and the incidence in men was 16 per 100,000 (3). In our case, consistent with the literature, the patient was male and 74 years

old. We believe that its prevalence in older age groups and males is related to cardiovascular risk factors.

The clinical presentation most commonly involves sudden onset of severe chest pain, but may also include aortic insufficiency, cardiac tamponade, and end-organ ischaemia (4). Although these cases typically present with severe clinical symptoms, they may occasionally present with a silent clinical course. In our case, there was clinically isolated epigastric pain and newly developed bradycardia. We should also consider aortic dissection in patients presenting to our emergency departments with newly developed bradycardia. Acute coronary syndrome and aortic dissection should also be included in the differential diagnosis of our patients with epigastric pain.

Stanford Type A aortic dissection typically presents with atypical symptoms such as chest pain, orthopnoea, and exertional dyspnoea, whereas Type B aortic dissection usually presents with back pain. Risk factors that increase aortic dissection include advancing age, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis, and renal failure (2). Our patient presented with epigastric chest pain and had a Type A dissection extending from the ascending aorta to the aortic arch, descending aorta, abdominal aorta, and both main iliac arteries and the right external iliac artery. The patient was

referred to our hospital from the district state hospital with a preliminary diagnosis of acute coronary syndrome. Although there were no signs of ischaemia on the electrocardiogram, the initial troponin test was negative. When making a differential diagnosis in patients with symptoms of acute coronary syndrome, we must not forget aortic dissection. Consistent with the literature, our patient had risk factors including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, coronary artery disease, high cholesterol, and arrhythmia. We believe that we should also practise preventive medicine by informing patients with uncontrolled or newly diagnosed hypertension who present to our emergency departments and consulting with them when necessary.

Controlling blood pressure is important in the initial management of patients with aortic dissection. The aim of hypertension treatment is to reduce stress on the aortic wall and limit the progression of the dissection. Although intravenous beta-blockers are recommended for treatment, systolic blood pressure should be titrated to between 100 and 120 mmHg (5-6). Since our patient's blood pressure remained around 110/80 mmHg during monitored follow-ups from the time of admission, we did not administer antihypertensive treatment.

In cases of aortic dissection, ischaemic and neurological problems also occur as a result

of occlusion caused by pressure on the false lumen (7-8). Our patient described a brief episode of fainting as presyncope. We should also suspect aortic dissection in patients presenting to the emergency department with syncope and presyncope.

It is quite difficult to make a differential diagnosis in patients with aortic dissection who present with atypical symptoms (9). We must remember that patients presenting to the emergency department with bradycardia and epigastric pain should undergo the necessary investigations as soon as possible, and that aortic dissection can also present with atypical symptoms and has a high mortality rate.

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